

From Security Concerns to ASRs (Academic Case Study)

This document summarizes the case study used in the paper and the initial step of the proposed method: starting from security concerns and transforming them into Architecturally Significant Requirements (ASRs). Note: the work describes a method (not a framework).

1. System context

System: an academic information system that manages sensitive data (e.g., academic records, personal information, results, and research data) and exposes multiple services through a service-oriented architecture.

Relevant characteristics: multiple services, centralized authentication/authorization, logging and monitoring of security events, and the need to ensure continuity of critical services.

2. Elicitation of concerns (Security Concerns)

- C1: Unauthorized users may access sensitive academic resources.
- C2: The system cannot reliably determine who executed a security-relevant action.
- C3: Services may become unavailable during DoS or under partial compromise.
- C4: A compromised service could propagate attacks to other parts of the system.

3. Transformation into ASRs (architectural drivers)

The concerns are consolidated into three ASRs (drivers) that guide architectural decisions. Each ASR is associated with security quality attributes (QA).

ID	ASR (statement)	Primary QA
ASR_1	Enforce fine-grained and dynamically evaluated access control over sensitive resources.	Confidentiality (primary); Integrity (sec.)
ASR_2	Provide tamper-evident audit trails and continuous monitoring of security-relevant actions.	Auditability
ASR_3	Maintain availability and graceful degradation under partial compromise or DoS-like conditions.	Availability

4. Operational definitions (for consistency across artifacts)

- ASR: a significant requirement that influences architectural decisions, typically tied to quality attributes.
- QA: a measurable quality attribute relevant to security (e.g., confidentiality, integrity, auditability, availability).
- Zero Trust principles: Verify Explicitly, Least-Privilege Access, Assume Breach.
- QAS: quality attribute scenario (source, stimulus, artifact, environment, response, response measure).

- SIG: Softgoal Interdependency Graph to model traceability among ASRs, QA, ZT principles, and mechanisms.

5. Output of this step

Output: a list of ASRs and their mapping to QA, which feeds the next steps of the method (decomposition into SIGs and mapping to QAS scenarios).

References

Aligned with the ICSA 2026 workshop paper: "Deriving Zero Trust-Oriented Security Scenarios from Architectural Requirements".